

THREE-DIODE MODEL AND SIMULATION OF PHOTOVOLTAIC (PV) CELLS

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ABSTRACT

Existing empirical solar cell models use one or two diodes. As the number of diodes in a model increases, the mathematical complexity in deriving model equations also increases. In this paper, a photovoltaic cell is modeled using three diodes. Non-linear mathematical equations governing the I-V and P-V characteristics are summarized and simulated using Matlab looping iterative method. All simulations were performed in Matlab. Comparison is made between all models (one, two and three-diode) for design verification. Results obtained show that as the number of diodes increases in a PV cell model, the open circuit voltage and maximum power decreases for a given set of PV cell parameters. The short circuit current remained at a fixed value irrespective of the number of diodes.

KEYWORDS: Photovoltaic, I-V characteristic, P-V characteristic, Three-diode model, Matlab

1. INTRODUCTION

To obtain the power-voltage (P-V) and current-voltage (I-V) characterization of a solar cell, a model of photovoltaic cell is required. A model is also needed to study and understand the behavior of a practical solar cell under different ecological conditions (Vivek and Sawle, 2015). A general and widespread method is to make use of an electrical equivalent circuit, which is primarily based on a light-generated current source connected in parallel to a p-n junction diode (Vivek and Sawle, 2015). Many models have been proposed for the simulation of a single solar cell or for a complete photovoltaic (PV) system at various solar intensities and temperature conditions as seen in (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2011; Eduardo Lorenzo, 1994; Jenny Nelson, 2003; Nielson, 1982; Vivek and Sawle, 2015; Gow and Manning, 1999; Yetayew and Jyothsna 2013; Aurel *et al.*, 2018; and Andreea *et al.*, 2017).

In (Dorin *et al.*, 2008; Eduardo, 1994; Nielson, 1982; Vivek and Sawle, 2015), single-diode photovoltaic cells are modeled and simulated. However, the single-diode model neglects the recombination effect of the diode (Vivek and Sawle, 2015). This makes the single diode model a fairly accurate model. To curb this setback, the two-diode model was introduced. Comparison between the one and two-diode models were performed in (Eduardo Lorenzo, 1994; Vivek and Sawle, 2015). Models compared in (Suthar *et*

al., 2013; Filippo *et al.*, 2013; Gow and Manning, 1999; Villaiva *et al.*, 2009; Ishaque *et al.*, 2011; Yuncong *et al.*, 2010 and Huan-Liang, 2010) show that the two-diode models produced fairly accurate results at low temperatures.

This paper presents modeling and simulation of a three-diode model of a photovoltaic cell. A third diode was added in parallel to the existing two-diode model and a study of its effects on the I-V and P-V characterization is presented. The objective of this work is to study and compare the one, two and three diode models to see the effect of an increase in the number of diodes in a simulation model.

2. EXISTING PHOTOVOLTAIC CELL MODELS

The empirical models so far rely on different values extracted from the I-V characteristic of photovoltaic cells and they approximate the characteristic equation of the solar panels using an analytical function (Dorin, Cristian, and Ciocan, 2008). In this section, a summary of existing models is presented.

I_L = Photocurrent; I_D = Diode current; I = Output current; V = Output voltage; q = Electron charge; n = Diode factor; k = Boltzmann constant; T = Operating temperature; I_0 = Diode saturation current; I_{sc} = Short circuit current; V_{oc} = Open circuit voltage; R_S = Series resistance; R_{SH} = Shunt resistance; P = Power

Figure 1: Ideal single-diode model

From Fig.1, using Kirchoff's current law,

$$I = I_L - I_D \tag{1}$$

The Shockley equation for an ideal diode is given by:

$$I_D = I_0 \left[\exp^{\frac{qV}{nkT}} - 1 \right] \tag{2}$$

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp^{\frac{qV}{nkT}} - 1 \right] \tag{3}$$

For n_s number of cells,

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp^{\frac{qV}{nn_s kT}} - 1 \right] \tag{4}$$

The open circuit voltage and short circuit current can be used to characterize a photovoltaic cell.

The short circuit current I_{SC} is obtained when $V = 0$ in (4)

Thus,

$$I_{SC} = I = I_L \tag{5}$$

The open circuit voltage V_{OC} is obtained when $I = 0$ in (4)

$$I_L = I_0 \left[\exp^{\frac{qV}{nkT}} - 1 \right]$$

$$V_{OC} = \frac{n_s nkT}{q} \ln \left[\frac{I_L}{I_0} + 1 \right] \tag{6}$$

Power

$$P = IV = \left[I_L - I_0 \left[\exp^{\frac{qV}{nn_s kT}} - 1 \right] \right] V \tag{7}$$

Figure 2: Single-diode model with series resistance

Using similar procedures in equations 1 – 7 in the analysis of Figure 2, we obtain:

$$I = I_L - I_D$$

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp^{\frac{q(V+I n_s R_s)}{n_s nkT}} - 1 \right] \tag{8}$$

$$I_{SC} = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp^{\frac{q I_{SC} R_s}{nkT}} - 1 \right] \tag{9}$$

$$V_{OC} = \frac{n_s nkT}{q} \ln \left[\frac{I_L}{I_0} + 1 \right] \tag{10}$$

$$P = \left[I_L - I_0 \left[\exp^{\frac{q(V+I n_s R_s)}{n_s nkT}} - 1 \right] \right] V \tag{11}$$

Figure 3: Single-diode model with series and shunt resistances

$$I = I_L - I_D - I_{SH} \quad (12)$$

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{nkT} - 1 \right] - \frac{V+IR_S}{R_{SH}} \quad (14)$$

$$I_{SH} = \frac{V+IR_S}{R_{SH}} \quad (13)$$

For n_s cells;

$$I = I_L - I_0 \left[\exp \frac{q(V+I n_s R_S)}{n_s n k T} - 1 \right] - \frac{V+I n_s R_S}{n_s R_{SH}} \quad (15)$$

Figure 4: Double-diode model with series and shunt resistances

$$I = I_L - I_{D1} - I_{D2} - I_{SH} \quad (16)$$

$$I = I_L - I_{O1} \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{n_1 k T} - 1 \right] - I_{O2} \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{n_2 k T} - 1 \right] - \frac{V+IR_S}{R_{SH}} \quad (17)$$

3. THREE DIODE MODEL

In the one and two-diode models highlighted above, internal losses and voltage drops caused by the inflow of current in a PV cell were represented in the model by the series resistance. The shunt resistance caters for the leakage current to ground in a practical PV cell. A single-diode model does not cater for the recombination effect of a diode as shown in (Vivek & Sawle, 2015); hence, another

diode is added in parallel to form the two-diode model. In this section, a third diode is added in parallel to the existing two-diode model and a study of its effects on the I-V and P-V characterization is presented. Two models are presented: 1. A model with only series resistance and 2. A model with both series and shunt resistances.

Figure 5: Three diode model with series resistance

Using similar arguments in equations 1 – 4 and equation 13, the following is obtained.

$$I = I_L - I_{D1} - I_{D2} - I_{D3} \tag{18}$$

$$I = I_L - I_{O1} \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{n_1 kT} - 1 \right] - I_{O2} \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{n_2 kT} - 1 \right] - I_{O3} \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{n_3 kT} - 1 \right] \tag{19}$$

Figure 6: three-diode model with series and shunt resistances

$$I = I_L - I_{D1} - I_{D2} - I_{D3} - I_{SH} \tag{20}$$

$$I = I_L - I_{O1} \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{n_1 kT} - 1 \right] - I_{O2} \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{n_2 kT} - 1 \right] - I_{O3} \left[\exp \frac{q(V+IR_S)}{n_3 kT} - 1 \right] - \frac{V+IR_S}{R_{SH}} \tag{21}$$

4. SIMULATION MODEL

In this section, the mathematical model used for simulation in Matlab is presented. The output current, I is derived based on the figures and equations in section III. The general equations for the photocurrent, I_L ; the diode saturation current, I_0 and the nominal diode saturation current, I_{0N} were obtained in (Vivek & Sawle, 2015). This

was then extended to the case of the three diode model using subscripts 1, 2 and 3. The simulations were then performed using Matlab looping iterative method. The results are presented in section 5.

Case 1: Model with no shunt resistance

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_L &= \frac{G}{G_N} [I_{LN} + K_I(T - T_N)] \\
 I_O &= I_{O1} = I_{O2} = I_{O3} = I_{ON} \left(\frac{T}{T_N}\right)^3 \exp\left[\frac{qE_g}{nk} \left(\frac{1}{T_N} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right] \\
 I_{ON} &= I_{ON1} = I_{ON2} = I_{ON3} = \frac{I_{SCN}}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{OCN}}{nV_{TN}}\right) - 1} \\
 I &= I_L - I_{O1} \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V+I R_S)}{n_1 k T}\right) - 1 \right] - I_{O2} \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V+I R_S)}{n_2 k T}\right) - 1 \right] - I_{O3} \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V+I R_S)}{n_3 k T}\right) - 1 \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Case 2: Model with shunt resistance

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_L &= \frac{G}{G_N} [I_{LN} + K_I(T - T_N)] \\
 I_O &= I_{O1} = I_{O2} = I_{O3} = I_{ON} \left(\frac{T}{T_N}\right)^3 \exp\left[\frac{qE_g}{nk} \left(\frac{1}{T_N} - \frac{1}{T}\right)\right] \\
 I_{ON} &= I_{ON1} = I_{ON2} = I_{ON3} = \frac{I_{SCN}}{\exp\left(\frac{V_{OCN}}{nV_{TN}}\right) - 1} \\
 I &= I_L - I_{O1} \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V+I R_S)}{n_1 k T}\right) - 1 \right] - I_{O2} \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V+I R_S)}{n_2 k T}\right) - 1 \right] - I_{O3} \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V+I R_S)}{n_3 k T}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V+I R_S}{R_{SH}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

Table 1: PV cell parameters

Parameters	Values
k	1.38065e-23 J/K
q	1.602e-19 C
I _{scn}	8.21 A
V _{ocn}	32.9 V
K _i	0.0032 A/K
T	25+273 K
T _n	25+273 K
G _n	1000 W/m ²
n	1.3 (1≤n≤2)
E _g	1.12 J
G	1000 W/m ²
R _s	0.2 Ω
R _{sh}	415 Ω

5. RESULTS

Case 1: Model with shunt resistance

Figure 7: Comparing the I-V characteristics of models with the same diode reality factor

Figure 8: Comparing the I-V characteristics of models with different diode reality factors (1.1, 1.2 and 1.3)

Figure 9: Comparing the P-V characteristics of models with the same diode reality factor

Figure 10: Comparing the P-V characteristics of models with different diode reality factors (1.1, 1.2 and 1.3)

Case 2: Model with no shunt resistance

Figure 11: Comparing the P-V characteristics of models with the same diode reality factor

Figure 12: Comparing the P-V characteristics of models with different diode reality factors (1.1, 1.2 and 1.3)

Figure 13: Comparing the I-V characteristics of models with the same diode reality factor

Figure 14: Comparing the I-V characteristics of models with different diode reality factors (1.1, 1.2 and 1.3)

6. DISCUSSION

In figure 7, a diode factor of 1.1 was used for the one, two and three diode models. Figure 7 shows that as the number of diodes increases, the open circuit voltage decreases from 33V to 31V. In figure 8, a diode factor of 1.1 was used for the single diode model, a diode factor of 1.2 was used for the two diode model and a diode factor of 1.3 was used for the three diode model. The plot shows that irrespective of variations in the diode reality factor, an increase in the number of diodes also results in a reduction in the open circuit voltage from 33V to 31V. It can be inferred that variations in the diode factor did not have an effect on the simulation result.

In figure 9, a diode factor of 1.1 was used for the one, two and three diode models. Figure 9 shows that as the number of diodes increases, the maximum power drawn reduces from 201W to 186W. In figure 10, a diode factor of 1.1 was used for the single diode model, a diode factor of 1.2 was used for the two diode model and a diode factor of 1.3 was used for the three diode model. It can be observed from figure 10 that as the number of diodes increases, the maximum power drawn reduces from 201W to 190W. It can be inferred that an increase in the diode factor from 1.1 to 1.3 causes 2.14% decrease in the power drawn.

From figures 11 and 12, it can be deduced that irrespective of variations in the diode reality factor, an increase in the number of diodes results in a reduction in the maximum power drawn. In figure 11, the power is reduced from 203W to 187W with a corresponding decrease in the open circuit voltage from 33V to 31V. In figure 12, the power is reduced from 203W to 191W with a corresponding decrease in the open circuit voltage from 33V to 31V. Also, it can be inferred that an increase in the diode factor from 1.1 to 1.3 causes 2.14% decrease in the power drawn.

Figures 13 and 14 show that irrespective of variations in the diode reality factor, an increase in the number of diodes also results in a reduction in the open circuit voltage from 33V to 31V. It can be inferred that variations in the diode factor also did not have an effect on the simulation result.

In all the simulations performed, the short circuit current remained at a fixed value of 8.21A.

7. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, as the number of diodes increases, the open circuit voltage for a given set of parameters of a photovoltaic cell reduces. However, the short circuit current

remains the same irrespective of the number of diodes. Also, an increase in the number of diodes reduces the maximum permissible power drawn from a PV cell. It is recommended that future work seeks to optimize the one, two and three-diode models to find the conditions under which all the three models produce identical simulation results.

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